

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

tinyHLS: a novel open source high level synthesis tool targeting hardware accelerators for artificial neural network inference

To cite this article: Ingo Hoyer *et al* 2025 *Physiol. Meas.* **46** 015002

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [EdgeECG: a lightweight edge-oriented network with dual criterion pruning for real-time ECG arrhythmia classification](#)
Jiayan Huang, Chuansheng Wang, Antoni Grau *et al.*
- [Efficient detection of cardiac arrhythmias using low-latency fpga-accelerated hybrid deep learning models](#)
Karthik Sekhar, Priyadarsini K and Jeba Sonia J
- [A novel deep learning package for electrocardiography research](#)
Hao Wen and Jingsu Kang

PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
30 August 2024REVISED
27 November 2024ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
10 January 2025PUBLISHED
29 January 2025

Original Content from
this work may be used
under the terms of the
[Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

Any further distribution
of this work must
maintain attribution to
the author(s) and the title
of the work, journal
citation and DOI.

tinyHLS: a novel open source high level synthesis tool targeting hardware accelerators for artificial neural network inference

Ingo Hoyer^{1,*} , Alexander Utz¹ , Christoph Hoog Antink² and Karsten Seidl^{1,3} ¹ Fraunhofer Institute for Microelectronic Circuits and Systems IMS, Duisburg, Germany² KIS* MED (AI Systems in Medicine), Technical University of Darmstadt, Darmstadt, Germany³ Department of Electronic Components and Circuits, University of Duisburg-Essen, Duisburg, Germany

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: tinyHLS@ims.fraunhofer.de

Keywords: HLS, biosignals, AI, RISC-V

Abstract

Objective. In recent years, wearable devices such as smartwatches and smart patches have revolutionized biosignal acquisition and analysis, particularly for monitoring electrocardiography (ECG). However, the limited power supply of these devices often precludes real-time data analysis on the patch itself. **Approach.** This paper introduces a novel Python package, tinyHLS (High Level Synthesis), designed to address these challenges by converting Python-based AI models into platform-independent hardware description language code accelerators. Specifically designed for convolutional neural networks, tinyHLS seamlessly integrates into the AI developer's workflow in Python TensorFlow Keras. Our methodology leverages a template-based hardware compiler that ensures flexibility, efficiency, and ease of use. In this work, tinyHLS is first-published featuring templates for several layers of neural networks, such as dense, convolution, max and global average pooling. In the first version, rectified linear unit is supported as activation. It targets one-dimensional data, with a particular focus on time series data. **Main results.** The generated accelerators are validated in detecting atrial fibrillation on ECG data, demonstrating significant improvements in processing speed (62-fold) and energy efficiency (4.5-fold). Quality of code and synthesizability are ensured by validating the outputs with commercial ASIC design tools. **Significance.** Importantly, tinyHLS is open-source and does not rely on commercial tools, making it a versatile solution for both academic and commercial applications. The paper also discusses the integration with an open-source RISC-V and potential for future enhancements of tinyHLS, including its application in edge servers and cloud computing. The source code is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-IMS/tinyHLS>

1. Introduction: challenges in embedded biosignal analysis

Over the past few years, wearable devices such as smartwatches and smart patches have created new opportunities for biosignal acquisition and analysis. Prominent examples include electrocardiography (ECG), photoplethysmography (PPG), and electromyography (EMG) (Liu *et al* 2019, Wu *et al* 2020, Mahdi *et al* 2024). Medical sensor patches, such as patch ECG devices, are an emerging trend and pose special challenges due to their compactness (section 1.1). A significant advancement in software-based analysis is the growing trend towards machine learning (ML) within the field of artificial intelligence (AI) (Matthews *et al* 2023). Combining both aspects, specialized digital hardware is a continuous field of research (section 1.2).

1.1. Motivation: trend towards wearable sensor patches for ECG monitoring

For ECG monitoring, the compactness of smart patches offers greater comfort for patients compared to standard Holter monitors. ECG is widely used to screen for heart arrhythmias such as atrial fibrillation (AF). This condition affects approximately 2% of adults, with its prevalence increasing with age. AF leads to a lower

Table 1. Emerging trends in ECG devices: comparison of patch ECG devices. Commercial devices only offer offline and remote analysis of the data, whereas research demonstrators offer local data analysis on the patch itself. Local analysis challenges the battery run-time and therefore the recording time.

Name	Rec.-Time	Analysis	References
CardioSTAT	2–14 d	offl.	Nault <i>et al</i> (2019), Icentia (2023)
Zio AT/XT	14 d	rem.	Turakhia <i>et al</i> (2013), Barrett <i>et al</i> (2014), iRHYTHM (2023)
ECG247	7 d	rem.	Sandberg <i>et al</i> (2023), mindtecstore (2023)
Nightingale V2	1 d	local	Lee <i>et al</i> (2019), Campero Jurado <i>et al</i> (2023), Holst Centre (2023)
ARTEMIS	7–14 d	local	Hoyer <i>et al</i> (2022a, 2022)

Table 2. State of the art: Biosignal ASICs for local, AI-driven analysis of data in research. All ASICs have been manually designed, without a high-level synthesis approach.

First Author	Algor.	Impl.	Tech.	References
LERCH	CNN	HW	130 nm	Lerch <i>et al</i> (2021)
HSU	SVM	RISC + Acc	90 nm	Hsu <i>et al</i> (2014)
CHEN	WLC/SVM	HW	40 nm	Chen <i>et al</i> (2017)
YIN	NN	HW	65 nm	Yin <i>et al</i> (2019)
VAN HELLEPUTTE	Various	ARM + Acc	180 nm	Van Helleputte <i>et al</i> (2014)

quality of life, earlier death, and strokes (Go *et al* 2001, Zink *et al* 2020, McIntyre *et al* 2022). Consequently, many commercial companies and research institutes have developed ECG patches in recent years (table 1).

To reliably detect AF, long recording times (e.g. two weeks) are needed (Turakhia *et al* 2013). Due to the limited power supply of ECG patches, such as a CR-2032 coin cell for the ECG247 patch (mindtecstore 2023) and the Zio AT patch (PRAXISDIENST 2021), many patches do not perform real-time data analysis on the patch itself. Instead, the data is either sent to a remote server (Zio AT/XT, ECG247) or collected and analyzed after the patch is removed (CardioSTAT). In research, there are approaches for on-patch data analysis (ARTEMIS, Nightingale V2). These approaches involve application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs) for signal processing, enabling the needed recording and analysis times, whilst having limited impact on patient comfort.

1.2. State of the art: digital hardware and high level synthesis

For real-time capability and energy efficiency, many ASICs have been manually developed featuring accelerators for AI inference (table 2). Since these are research results, they are implemented in cost-efficient technologies ranging from 40 nm to 180 nm. The AI algorithms applied for biosignal processing range from convolutional neural networks (CNNs) (LERCH, table 2) to support vector machines (HSU, CHEN), and to flexible, software-based implementations (VAN HELLEPUTTE). Most of the ASICs feature dedicated hardware implementations (HWs). Two feature a microprocessor (RISC-V or ARM architecture) with specialized accelerators for AI inference. HLS was not deployed to develop the circuits. The diversity of these platforms illustrates the need for fast design of hardware platforms and flexibility of frameworks used for AI algorithms.

To reduce the effort for circuit design, high-level synthesis (HLS) is a suitable approach. Various tools have evolved in recent years, focusing on input languages such as MATLAB, OpenCL, or C/C++ (Lahti *et al* 2018). Given that Python is one of the most common languages used for AI applications (Sengupta 2021), there is a gap to be closed between Python and HLS tools.

One approach is to build a conversion tool from Python to an intermediate representation (e.g. C++ with pragmas), which can then be input into an HLS tool. An open-source conversion tool called hls4ml (Duarte *et al* 2018, Fahim *et al* 2021, FastML Team 2023) currently supports commercial toolchains such as Vivado HLS, Intel HLS, and Vitis HLS in the backend (table 3). However, hls4ml inherits the same drawbacks as these commercial toolchains, such as target-specific architecture and usage restrictions. As these toolchains are provided by FPGA manufacturers like AMD for Vivado and Vitis, and Intel, they are primarily designed for FPGA implementations. The parameter memory is mapped directly onto the RAM blocks of the target FPGA. In the hardware description language (HDL) code, this results in constructs such as `readmemh` commands and `initial begin` blocks in Verilog that are intended for testbenches and are not synthesizable by ASIC synthesis toolchains but are supported by some FPGA toolchains. Additionally, the end-user license agreement prohibits the use of the HDL code on platforms not intended by the FPGA manufacturer that provides the HLS software.

Table 3. Existing HLS frameworks. Most frameworks have a C++ Frontend. Using Python as an input requires additional preprocessing e.g. through hls4ml.

Name	Input	Output	Backend	References
VivadoHLS	C++	HDL for FPGAs	standalone	(AMD (2022))
XLS	C++	(System)Verilog	standalone	(Google (2024))
LegUp	C/C++	Verilog	standalone	(Canis <i>et al</i> (2013); Tierney (2020))
hls4ml	Python	see backend	VivadoHLS	(Fahim <i>et al</i> (2021); Duarte <i>et al</i> (2018); FastML Team (2023))

1.3. Scope of this work

Due to the mentioned gap between Python-based AI models and HDL, the main contribution of this work is to develop a tool that closes this gap without using complex intermediate representations. The targeted applications of this contribution are specifically CNNs in time-series analysis, which makes a template-based approach suitable. Additionally, this work aims to provide a platform-independent option, addressing the challenges that the existing tool pose. After the tool is introduced (section 2), it is validated (section 3) on three CNNs to generate results (section 4) and a basis for discussion (section 5). Lastly, this paper points out what future applications and expansions of the tool are possible (section 6).

2. Novel Python Package: tinyHLS

tinyHLS is a tool, that converts Python-based AI models, particularly CNNs, into platform-independent HDL code accelerators. The layer-by-layer structure of these models is leveraged in this template-based hardware compiler. It is designed for seamless integration with the AI developer's workflow in Python TensorFlow Keras (figure 1).

2.1. Methodology

In contrast to the mentioned available tools, tinyHLS does not generate HDL code generically. Neural networks have a layer-oriented architecture, where a limited number of layer types are combined to build the overall network. Therefore, a template-based approach that offers flexibility in input size, data type, and layer combinations is deemed sufficient. The overall principle is shown in figure 2.

First, templates for the required layers have to be developed. Initially, the tool focuses on 1D layers such as Convolution (Conv), Global Average Pooling (GAP), MaxPooling, and dense layers. For each layer, a module is developed that includes the required functionality. Each module is tested with a set of input values, and its outputs are compared to the inference results of the equivalent Python layer.

Once the individual layers are successfully validated, the integration of the layers into CNNs must be implemented. The simple pipelining of the tool features start signals and out-enable signals to ensure the correct flow of data through the layers. Additionally, to reduce hardware requirements, a more advanced pipelining is implemented to interface between the convolution layer and the pooling layers. Since not all results from the convolution layer are required for the first mathematical operation of the pooling, the pooling can start its first calculation during the operation of the convolution layer.

To use the modules as templates later, parameters for flexible adaptation are necessary. The layer number is used to name registers and signals to avoid duplicate names. Quantization parameters, including bit width and the number of bits for integers, are also included. These parameters are used in comments to make the code more understandable and trustworthy. Further parameters come from the Python model, such as the number of input and output channels, their lengths, kernel size, strides, and a parameter for the activation function.

Implementing weights is a challenge for a platform-independent approach. Conventional methods for an SoC involve implementing memory IP and setting it while programming the microcontroller. However, this requires knowledge of the specific ASIC technology or FPGA being used, making the system platform-dependent. Therefore, the weights and biases are implemented as assigned wires (listings 1 and 2).

Since Python TensorFlow Keras natively uses floating-point datatype, tinyHLS must convert to fixed-point to make the implementation more hardware-efficient. The conversion supports quantization to 32, 24, 16, or 8 bits and offers flexible definition of the integer part.

```
reg [BIT_WIDTH-1:0] mat_temp1;
`include "weights/weights0.v"
```

Listing 1. Definition of weight matrix and include statement for weight assignments.

```
assign mat1[0] = 32'h00119f76;
assign mat1[1] = 32'hffeb84d2;
```

Listing 2. Assignments of the weights in `weights0.v`.

```
network_hdl.append("//Layer " + str(i) + " : DENSE LAYER//\n")
network_hdl.append("reg [" + str(n_bits) + "-1:0] i_" + str(i) + ";\n")
network_hdl.append("reg [" + str(n_bits) + "-1:0] j_" + str(i) + ";\n")
[...]
network_hdl2.append("//Layer " + str(i) + " : DENSE LAYER//\n")
network_hdl2.append("always @(*) begin\n")
[...]
network_hdl1.append("//Layer " + str(i) + " : DENSE LAYER//\n")
network_hdl1.append("always @ (posedge clk or negedge reset_n) begin\n")
network_hdl1.append("\tif(!reset_n) begin\n")
```

Listing 3. Abstract from `translate` to `verilog.py`: Parameters for the layers are set (`i`, `n_bits`). Register definitions, sequential and combinatorial blocks are clearly separated for readability and synthesizability.

One of the goals of this tool is to provide high-quality code that is platform-independent and synthesizable for ASIC technologies. Hence the HDL code is clearly divided into signal definitions, combinatorial logic and sequential logic with the according coding style to ensure synthesizability (listing 3). Synthesizability is also verified using Cadence® Genus using a 180 nm technology (Cadence 2022a). Additionally, code reviews have been conducted with a group of experienced developers.

The templates are then included as individual lines in Python scripts (listing 3). This allows for many degrees of freedom, such as adapting the names of signals and parameters and organizing the code for better understanding. As mentioned, three sections are separated: signal definitions, combinatorial logic, and sequential logic. The layers are clearly marked with comments within the sections. Usage of the scripts is explained in section 2.2.

The tool has been tested internally on several CNN architectures that feature the supported layers. To ensure continuous functionality, the GitHub repository includes a workflow with a test CNN and its simulation based on open-source tools (section 2.3). The internal development repository includes further tests, including the mentioned synthesis setup.

The generated accelerators feature a simple native interface with the inputs to the CNN, its outputs, a start signal, and an output-enable signal, similar to the layers themselves. Additionally, the standard signals clock and low-active reset are provided. To simplify integration into an SoC, a wrapper module with an AHB-Lite interface is provided in the repository (ARM 2006). It can seamlessly be integrated into memory-mapped architectures, e.g. as a peripheral to the open-source AIRISC RISC-V processor (Fraunhofer IMS 2021, 2023). This embedded microprocessor implements the RV32IM set of instructions. The interface also features parameters such as the base address to make it adaptable to the SoC's memory map. The base address features the control register with the start and stop signals. The next address can be written to set the inputs to the CNN or read to retrieve the outputs of the CNN. The control register offers the possibility to poll whether the accelerator has finished. Alternatively, to avoid actively waiting, an interrupt can be used. To include the accelerator into C-based software projects, a hardware abstraction layer (HAL) is provided that supports both options.

2.2. Installation and usage

tinyHLS is recommended to be used in a conda environment (Anaconda 2024) and is validated with Python 3.9.12. To install tinyHLS into the environment, the repository from GitHub needs to be cloned (Fraunhofer IMS 2024). To create the environment, an `environment.yml` file is included in the repository. After that, the environment needs to be activated and the installation commands run (listing 4).

```
$ conda env create -f environment.yml
$ conda activate tinyHLS
```

Listing 4. Installation of tinyHLS into the conda environment.

Figure 1. tinyHLS workflow: first, the standard Python environments are used to create and optimize the AI model. Second, tinyHLS generates the hardware accelerator from the Python model, including the bus and interrupt interface, a testbench to validate the accelerator, and C libraries to use the accelerator from a microcontroller.

Figure 2. tinyHLS method: based on the Verilog templates for the layers, testbench and interface, the accelerator is generated by the python scripts.

The package is designed to seamlessly integrate with the user’s standard Python TensorFlow Keras workflow (Google 2021) (figure 1). The model can either be predesigned and imported or trained in the same Python script from which tinyHLS is run. tinyHLS outputs the neural network accelerator in Verilog, as well as a testbench for verification. The accelerator also features an interrupt and bus interface and includes the weights of the AI model. Software libraries in C to control the accelerator as a memory-mapped peripheral are also included in tinyHLS.

Using tinyHLS involves two main steps (figure 3). First, the weights from the Python model are extracted, exported as a .hex file, and then converted into Verilog files. Second, the model is translated into the accelerator module, and a testbench is generated. An example script is provided in the repository for demonstration purposes.

2.3. Example script in the repository

The example is provided in the `test.py` file in the repository. First, a simple test model is created (ln. 49–101) with the following layers:

- Conv1D,
- MaxPool1D,
- Conv1D,
- GAP1D, and
- two dense layers.

A couple of parameters need to be set for tinyHLS. As tinyHLS uses hardware-friendly fixed-point quantization, the total bit width and the integer part of the representation need to be set (ln. 103–104). Then the output directory is set (ln. 106), before the weights are extracted (ln. 110). The next lines (ln. 112–120) set the parameters for the conversion of weights and bias to Verilog includes (ln. 122–124). After that, the model is translated into the Verilog accelerator (ln. 128) and the testbench is created (ln. 130). To provide the user additional feedback in the terminal, an end statement is printed to the terminal (ln. 132).

3. Validation

Three sets of experiments are performed for thorough validation. First, the tool is used with the detection of AF in ECG Signals. Second, to show transferability, the tool is applied in the estimation of the heart rate from a photoplethysmogram (PPG) recording. A third benchmark is generated from the test example in the repository.

All three tests and comparisons follow the same approach (figure 4), but feature a different CNN (figure 5). With the proposed method, the AI model in Python is converted into HDL Code (Verilog). To compare the results to a common embedded implementation approach, the AI model is converted into a C-Program using Keras2C and Onnx2C (Conlin *et al* 2021, kraiskil 2024). The program is compiled and then loaded into the memory of the standard SoC that is provided in the GitHub repository of the AIRISC microcontroller (Fraunhofer IMS 2023). The SoC setup does not feature RAM-IP but uses an idealized model to save simulation and synthesis time.

The SoCs are synthesized using Cadence[®] Genus[™] (Cadence 2022a). Post-synthesis simulation was used to verify the correct functionality of the CNN and further validate tinyHLS. Place and route were performed using Cadence[®] Innovus[™] (Cadence 2022b) for the X-FAB XH018 technology (X-FAB 2024). Using Cadence[®] Xcelium[™] (Cadence 2024), activity files were exported to measure the actual power consumption of the circuit for the real application in the place and route tool.

3.1. AF in ECG Signals

As illustrated in the introduction, the detection of AF is a key challenge for compact, lightweight smart patches. The CNN used was first presented by LERCH (Lerch *et al* 2021) (table 2). It features four convolution layers, a GAP layer, and two dense layers (figure 5). Minor modifications were made, and standard convolutions were used instead of the SepConv used by LERCH. Its output consists of two one-bit values: whether there is AF or whether it is a normal sinus rhythm.

The modifications include quantization to an 8-bit fixed-point datatype. Since 91% of the input data was in the range from -7 to 7 , 3 bits for integer representation were set and 4 bits for the representation of fractions. To further reduce hardware requirements, the model was pruned by 75%. The model was fitted before and after the pruning. For the software comparison, C-Code was generated with Keras2C (Conlin *et al* 2021, Conlin 2022), same as for the test CNN.

A dataset from Charité—Universitätsmedizin Berlin was used. It was collected from the clinical trial ‘Telemedical Interventional Monitoring in Heart Failure’ (TIM-HF, NCT00543881), which comprises 22 400 ECG recordings from 354 patients with heart failure (Koehler *et al* 2011). For the training phase, 16 000 samples were utilized. The remaining 6400 samples, equally divided into 3200 positive and 3200 negative samples, were reserved for testing.

To provide access to the source code of the proposed method, the experiments were repeated with the publicly available dataset from PhysioNet (Goldberger *et al* 2000). In particular, the MIT-BIH Normal Sinus Rhythm Database and the MIT-BIH AF Database were used (Moody 1983, Moody and Roger 1999, 2000). The preprocessing, training and translation with tinyHLS can be found in the `ecg_example.py` within the tinyHLS repository. Although the model appears to overfit on this dataset, which could be addressed by a data scientist as a contribution in the future, this issue is of limited relevance to our primary focus on demonstrating the toolbox’s capability to generate HDL from Python models, with an emphasis on acceleration.

3.2. Heart rate in PPG signals

The transferability of the method is also shown for estimating the heart rate in PPG signals. Though this is a comparably simple task, it is often performed in wearables with limited energy supply (Biswas *et al* 2019). Hence, this requires a high level of energy efficiency which can be provided by dedicated hardware accelerators.

One additional aspect of transferability is the use of PyTorch in this demonstration. Though PyTorch differs from TensorFlow Keras in terms of layer names and descriptions, a wrapper function can be written that translates one description into the other. The translated description can then be used as an input for tinyHLS. This example is provided in the `ppg_example.py` file in the tinyHLS repository and the translation from the PyTorch to Keras description is the `convert_model_to_json` function. Please note that this method is considered experimental and hence not yet a feature of tinyHLS itself.

For training and testing, the BIDMC PPG and Respiration Dataset is used (Pimentel *et al* 2017, 2018). The structure of the CNN is similar to the one for ECG classification, though only one channel with 75 values is considered, only one value (heart rate) is the output, and the internal number of channels in-between the layers as well as the kernel size is different. The details can be seen from the code in the repository.

Converting the model into C for comparison also requires a different toolbox than the ECG and test model, as it uses PyTorch instead of Keras. Hence Keras2C cannot be used. A suitable alternative is Onnx2C (kraiskil 2024).

4. Results

Main result of this work is the Python package tinyHLS itself, that is open-source available on Github (Fraunhofer IMS 2024). It features template-based accelerator generation for 1D CNNs and is platform independent. The following discusses the validation results.

The HW shows a speedup factor of 62.2 compared to the software implementation (table 4) for the time-series analysis of ECG signals and factor of 731.0 for the PPG. For the test CNN, a factor of 1082.3 is achieved. Due to the increase in the critical path, the speedup factor is higher for the runtime in clock cycles for the ECG classification and lower for the test CNN. While the runtime of the software-based implementations is in the area of a couple of seconds, the inference in hardware can be achieved in a couple of milliseconds (PPG), depending on the complexity of the CNN.

The accuracy of the CNN for ECG processing with the Charité dataset is 95.41% in software and 94.51% after pruning, quantization and HW. As the input data was quantized, the software model has the same performance. For the PPG the root mean squared error (RMSE) is in software 5.74 and in hardware 6.28. For the test CNN, the network is not trained on a realistic, labeled dataset and hence the accuracy cannot be quantified.

In terms of area consumption, the accelerators require much more area than the processor. For the ECG accelerator, 26.5 times the area of the processor are required due to its complexity. For the PPG accelerator 15.7 times, and for the test CNN only 1.2 times the area is needed.

The hardware-implementation demonstrates higher energy efficiency. For the test-CNN, 99.8% of the energy can be saved and 77.9% for the ECG classification. 96.6% of energy per inference can be saved for the PPG application.

Table 4. Silicon area needed, runtime in clock cycles (cc) and in ms, as well as the critical path of the hardware implementation (HW Impl.) using tinyHLS and the software implementation on the microcontroller for the ECG processing CNN, the heart rate estimation for PPG and the simple test-CNN as application (Appl.). Runtime (RT) in μs is measured considering the critical path (CP). For the software-based implementation, the silicon area is the area for the AIRISC, which also has to be implemented for controlling purposes and has to be calculated on top of the area values of the hardware accelerators. The energy per inference (E_{Inf}) is estimated after placement and routing, based on an activity file for the concrete application. Please note that the exact values may vary depending on the optimization settings in Synthesis, Place and Route.

Impl.	Appl.	Area in mm^2	NAND- equation	RT in cc	CP in ns	RT in ms	E_{Inf} in mJ
HW	ECG	22.15	2207 319	2046 256	36.38	74.478	41.23
	PPG	13.10	1305 457	155 030	30.42	4.716	5.57
	Test	0.97	97 171	1243	28.26	0.035	0.003
SW	ECG	0.837	83 409	15 234 6747	30.42	4633.201	186.74
	PPG			11 337 8124		3447.338	138.99
	Test			1245 259		37.881	1.53

5. Discussion

The Python package tinyHLS can be easily installed and used on a trained TensorFlow Keras model with just four commands. It does not depend on any commercial tools and is open-source on GitHub. Though the tool itself is provided under GPLv3 (Free Software Foundation 2007), there is an exception included that allows the outputs of the tool to be used under terms of the user's choice. The exact wording can be found in the documentation in the repository. This means that changes to the tool itself have to be published; however, the user of the tool can integrate, commercialize, and distribute the outputs of the tool quite freely.

The validation results show, that the HWs overall achieve lower energy requirements and lower run-times (figure 6), hence real-time capability. Particularly for wearables, these are two critical factors (Biswas *et al* 2019). A major disadvantage of the implementation in hardware is the immense silicon area. In common designs, memory takes about half of the digital part's area. Typical values are e.g. 128 kB (Van Helleputte *et al* 2014), whereas here the accelerator for ECG processing requires as much area 400 kB SRAM would (Hoyer *et al* 2023). Hence designers have to carefully consider, if the advantages in latency and energy consumption are worth the area requirements. The loss of accuracy due to the optimization for the embedded domain is neglectable, the overall accuracy falls within the realistic range for similar CNNs and similar datasets (Biswas *et al* 2019, Erdenebayar *et al* 2019).

Comparing the implementation to other tools and manual implementations is challenging, as technology node, network topology and implementation methodology rarely match well. In this case of ECG classification, an older implementation of a quite similar CNN exists (Lerch *et al* 2021). It requires 5 mm^2 in 130 nm technology. Estimating an equivalent area for both implementations from the technologies used, this means that the tinyHLS implementation requires about 2.3 times the area. The literature implementation has a inference run-time of $142 \mu\text{s}$, which is 510 times faster. This shows, that a manual implementation can be much more efficient, though it can be expected that the pipelined structure of tinyHLS enables serial processing of the ECG traces. Also the literature implementation uses latches instead of flip-flops, which are not accepted by all design flows, but are more area-efficient. There may be many more reasons, why there is a huge gap in the results. We believe that an implementation with tinyHLS is a good compromise between a software-based implementation and a highly-optimized manual implementation that comes at high non-recurring engineering cost.

6. Conclusion and outlook

This paper presents the novel Python package tinyHLS and a method for generating application-specific hardware accelerators in Verilog based on a model description in Python. Automatically generated testbenches ensure functional correctness. The accelerators significantly reduce the latency of the classification, which has to be considered against the increase in required silicon area. As the output is platform-independent HDL code, the tool's outputs could also be used on an FPGA.

Benefits of the solution are faster computation and higher energy efficiency compared to a software-based implementation at the cost of largely increased silicon area. A manual design of the accelerator may be superior, but requires a designer to work many months. An optimal choice can only be made on a case-by-case basis.

Contributions to the tool are welcome in the GitHub repository. To support more layers and data types, templates have to be created, verified, and included in the Python scripts. For image data, these steps are

currently under investigation. Further advancements of the tool could also implement other types of algorithms, such as support vector machines or decision trees. To enable integration with more microcontrollers (e.g. ARM), an AXI interface might be beneficial. Besides use in the design of Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices, the methodology could be transferred toward edge servers or even cloud computing. However, these applications would require a high level of reconfigurability and hence likely use a reconfigurable array, such as an FPGA or a more AI-specific reconfigurable array.

Data availability statement

The datasets provided by Charité—Universitätsmedizin Berlin are not publicly available due to ethical and privacy restrictions. The data that support the findings of this work can be made available upon reasonable request from the authors. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

Acknowledgment

This research has been funded in part by the project CLEVER (Project ID 101097560), which is supported by the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking and its members (including top-up funding by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)). Parts of this work are derived from the ARTEMIS project for AI-based real-time detection of AF and integration into a wearable medical sensor device, funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) under Grant No. 13GW0579D in the program ‘Medizintechnische Lösungen für eine digitale Gesundheitsversorgung’.

Use of generative AI tools

This manuscript was edited with the assistance of OpenAI’s language model to enhance clarity, readability, and consistency. All suggestions were critically reviewed and accepted or modified by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final content. No AI tools were used to create, alter, or manipulate original research data or results.

Informed consent statement

The study TIM-HF, which provided the data, complied with good clinical practice in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and the laws and regulations applicable in Germany. Written approval from the appropriate ethics committees was obtained. Patients provided written informed consent for participation in the clinical study and medical analysis of their data.

ORCID iDs

Ingo Hoyer <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7877-6544>
Alexander Utz <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1274-4563>
Christoph Hoog Antink <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7948-8181>
Karsten Seidl <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6197-5037>

References

- AMD 2022 Vivado (available at: www.xilinx.com/support/university/vivado.html) (Accessed 13 March 2022)
- Anaconda 2024 Conda documentation (available at: <https://conda.io/projects/conda/en/latest/index.html>) (Accessed 24 January 2022)
- ARM 2006 Amba 3 ahb-lite protocol. V1.0
- Barrett P M et al 2014 Comparison of 24-hour holter monitoring with 14-day novel adhesive patch electrocardiographic monitoring *Am. J. Med.* **127** 95–e11
- Biswas D, Simões-Capela N, Van Hoof C and Van Helleputte N 2019 Heart rate estimation from wrist-worn photoplethysmography: a review *IEEE Sens. J.* **19** 6560–70
- Cadence 2022a Genus synthesis solution (available at: www.cadence.com/ko_KR/home/tools/digital-design-and-signoff/synthesis/genus-synthesis-solution.html) (Accessed 13 March 2022)
- Cadence 2022b Innovus implementation system (available at: www.cadence.com/ko_KR/home/tools/digital-design-and-signoff/soc-implementation-and-floorplanning/innovus-implementation-system.html) (Accessed 13 March 2022)
- Cadence 2024 Xcelium logic simulator (available at: www.cadence.com/en_US/home/tools/system-design-and-verification/simulation-and-testbench-verification/xcelium-simulator.html) (Accessed 13 November 2024)
- Campero Jurado I et al 2023 Signal quality analysis for long-term ECG monitoring using a health patch in cardiac patients *Sensors* **23** 2130
- Canis A et al 2013 Legup: an open-source high-level synthesis tool for FPGA-based processor/accelerator systems *ACM Trans. Embed. Comput. Syst.* **13** 1–27
- Chen Z, Luo J, Lin K, Wu J, Zhu T, Xiang X and Meng J 2017 An energy-efficient ECG processor with weak-strong hybrid classifier for arrhythmia detection *IEEE Trans. Circ. Syst. II* **65** 948–52
- Conlin R 2022 Keras2c (available at: <https://github.com/PlasmaControl/keras2c>) (Accessed 30 October 2022)
- Conlin R, Erickson K, Abbate J and Kolemen E 2021 Keras2c: a library for converting keras neural networks to real-time compatible C *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.* **100** 104182
- Duarte J et al 2018 Fast inference of deep neural networks in FPGAs for particle physics *JINST* **13** 07027
- Erdenebayar U, Kim H, Park J-U, Kang D and Lee K-J 2019 Automatic prediction of atrial fibrillation based on convolutional neural network using a short-term normal electrocardiogram signal *J. Korean Med. Sci.* **34** e64
- Fahim F et al 2021 hls4ml: an open-source codesign workflow to empower scientific low-power machine learning devices (arXiv:2103.05579)
- FastML Team 2023 fastmachinelearning/hls4ml (available at: <https://github.com/fastmachinelearning/hls4ml>)
- Fraunhofer I M S 2021 Airisc family (available at: www.airisc.de) (Accessed 24 December 2022)
- Fraunhofer I M S 2023 Airisc - the risc-v processor for embedded AI (available at: https://github.com/Fraunhofer-IMS/airisc_core_complex) (Accessed 24 August 2024)
- Fraunhofer I M S 2024 tinyhls (available at: <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-IMS/tinyHLS>) (Accessed 31 August 2024)
- Free Software Foundation 2007 Gnu general public license 3 (available at: www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.html) (Accessed 26 August 2024)
- Go A S et al 2001 Prevalence of diagnosed atrial fibrillation in adults: national implications for rhythm management and stroke prevention: the anticoagulation and risk factors in atrial fibrillation (atria) study *JAMA* **285** 2370–5
- Goldberger A L et al 2000 PhysioBank, physioToolkit and physionet: components of a new research resource for complex physiologic signals *Circulation* **101** e215–20
- Google 2021 Keras (available at: <https://keras.io/>) (Accessed 24 January 2022)
- Google 2024 Xls: accelerated hw synthesis (available at: <https://google.github.io/xls/>) (Accessed 23 June 2023)
- Holst Centre 2023 Health patch - holstcentre (available at: <https://executivereport.holstcentre.com/innovation-updates/health-vitality/health-patch/>) (Accessed 17 April 2023)
- Hoyer I et al 2022 Detection of atrial fibrillation with an optimized neural network on a risc-v-based microcontroller for efficient integration into ECG patches 2022 *IEEE Int. Symp. on Medical Measurements and Applications (MeMeA)* pp 1–6
- Hoyer I, Utz A, Lüdecke A, Kappert H, Rohr M, Antink C H and Seidl K 2023 Design of hardware accelerators for optimized and quantized neural networks to detect atrial fibrillation in patch ECG device with risc-v *Sensors* **23** 2703
- Hoyer I, Utz A, Lüdecke A, Rohr M, Antink C H and Seidl K 2022a Inference runtime of a neural network to detect atrial fibrillation on customized risc-v-based hardware *Curr. Dir. Biomed. Eng.* **8** 703–6
- Hsu S-Y, Ho Y, Chang P-Y, Su C and Lee C-Y 2014 A 48.6-to-105.2 μ w machine learning assisted cardiac sensor SOC for mobile healthcare applications *IEEE J. Solid-State Circ.* **49** 801–11
- Icentia 2023 Introducing cardiostat: up to 14 days of ambulatory ECG monitoring (available at: www.cardiostat.com/professionals) (Accessed 17 April 2023)
- iRHYTHM 2023 Zio monitoring (available at: www.irhythmtech.com/providers/zio-service/zio-monitors) (Accessed 17 April 2023)
- Koehler F et al 2011 Telemedical interventional monitoring in heart failure investigators. Impact of remote telemedical management on mortality and hospitalizations in ambulatory patients with chronic heart failure: the telemedical interventional monitoring in heart failure study *Circulation* **123** 1873–80
- kraiskil 2024 onnx2c (available at: <https://github.com/kraiskil/onnx2c>) (Accessed 30 October 2024)
- Lahti S, Sjövall P, Vanne J and Hämmäläinen T D 2018 Are we there yet? a study on the state of high-level synthesis *IEEE Trans. Comput.-Aided Des. Integr. Circ. Syst.* **38** 898–911
- Lee S, Grundlehner B, van der Westen R G, Polito S and Van Hoof C 2019 Nightingale v2: low-power compact-sized multi-sensor platform for wearable health monitoring 2019 *41st Annual Int. Conf. IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)* (IEEE) pp 1290–3

- Lerch R, Hosseini B, Gembaczka P, Fink G A, Lüdecke A, Brack V, Ercan F, Utz A and Seidl K 2021 Design of an artificial neural network circuit for detecting atrial fibrillation in ECG signals *2021 IEEE Sensors* pp 1–4
- Liu S-H, Lin C-B, Chen Y, Chen W, Huang T-S and Hsu C-Y 2019 An EMG patch for the real-time monitoring of muscle-fatigue conditions during exercise *Sensors* **19** 3108
- Mahdi M M, Gharghan S K, Mohammed S L and Ibrahim I A 2024 Smart patch for non-invasive blood pressure monitoring in epileptic seizure patients via the sole *J. Tech.* **6** 10–20
- Matthews J, Kim J and Yeo W-H 2023 Advances in biosignal sensing and signal processing methods with wearable devices *Anal. Sens.* **3** e202200062
- McIntyre W F et al 2022 Estimated incidence of previously undetected atrial fibrillation on a 14-day continuous electrocardiographic monitor and associated risk of stroke *EP Europace* **24** 1058–64
- mindtecstore 2023 ECG 247 - long-term ECG sensor with plaster - single pack (available at: www.mindtecstore.com/norgesplaster-ecg247-long-term-ecg-patch-with-plaster-for-self-testing-at-home-single-pack) (Accessed 17 April 2022)
- Moody G 1983 A new method for detecting atrial fibrillation using RR intervals *Proc. Comput. Cardiol.* **10** 227–30 (available at: <https://physionet.org/content/afdb/1.0.0/>)
- Moody G and Roger M 1999 Mit-bih normal sinus rhythm database (available at: <https://physionet.org/content/nsrdb/1.0.0/>) (Accessed 31 October 2024)
- Moody G and Roger M 2000 Mit-bih atrial fibrillation database (available at: <https://physionet.org/content/afdb/1.0.0/>) (Accessed 31 October 2024)
- Nault I et al 2019 Validation of a novel single lead ambulatory ECG monitor—cardiostat™—compared to a standard ecg holter monitoring *J. Electrocardiol.* **53** 57–63
- Pimentel M A F, Johnson A E W, Charlton P H, Birrenkott D, Watkinson P J, Tarassenko L and Clifton D A 2017 Toward a robust estimation of respiratory rate from pulse oximeters *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **64** 1914–23
- Pimentel M A F, Johnson A E W, Charlton P H, Clifton D A 2018 Bidmc PPG and respiration dataset (available at: <https://physionet.org/content/bidmc/1.0.0/>) (Accessed 31 October 2024)
- PRAXISDIENST 2021 Seltene herzzrhythmusstörungen diagnostizieren - mit dem at-patch 14 tage langzeit-ekg (available at: www.praxisdienst.de/Diagnostik/Fachspezifische+Diagnostik/EKG+Geraete/AT+Patch+14+Tage+Langzeit+EKG.html?speed=1&gclid=Cj0KCQiAzfuNBhCGARIsAD1nu-8Zf7NFFNGC9VxiSpFVTcMEeVNNNe-GIAVNs5vMCNOyCSjRC4zq_ey0aAivYEAALw_wcB) (Accessed 7 October 2023)
- Sandberg E L, Halvorsen S, Berge T, Grimsmo J, Atar D, Fensli R, Grenne B L and Jortveit J 2023 Fully digital self-screening for atrial fibrillation with patch electrocardiogram *Europace* **25** euad075
- Sengupta S 2021 Programming languages used in AI *Artificial Intelligence* (Chapman and Hall/CRC) pp 29–35
- Tierney M 2020 Legup computing, a u of t engineering startup, acquired by u.s.-based microchip technology (available at: www.utoronto.ca/news/legup-computing-u-t-engineering-startup-acquired-us-based-microchip-technology) (Accessed 25 June 2023)
- Turakhia M P et al 2013 Diagnostic utility of a novel leadless arrhythmia monitoring device *Am. J. Cardiol.* **112** 520–4
- Van Helleputte N et al 2014 A 345 μ w multi-sensor biomedical soc with bio-impedance, 3-channel ECG, motion artifact reduction and integrated DSP *IEEE J. Solid-State Circ.* **50** 230–44
- Wu T, Wu F, Qiu C, Redouté J-M and Yuce M R 2020 A rigid-flex wearable health monitoring sensor patch for iot-connected healthcare applications *IEEE Internet Things J.* **7** 6932–45
- X-FAB 2024 Our technology portfolio (available at: www.xfab.com/technology) (Accessed 3 November 2024)
- Yin S, Kim M, Kadedotad D, Liu Y, Bae C, Kim S J, Cao Y and Seo J-s 2019 A 1.06 μ w smart ECG processor in 65-nm CMOS for real-time biometric authentication and personal cardiac monitoring *IEEE J. Solid-State Circ.* **54** 2316–26
- Zink M D et al 2020 Screen-detected atrial fibrillation predicts mortality in elderly subjects *EP Europace* **23** 29–38